

THE ORETICAL ASPECTS OF PROVIDING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH INCREASING THE INNOVATION AND INVESTMENT ACTIVITY OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Anotation.

While the countries belonging to the group of innovation leaders are undergoing a technological revolution, developing countries are solving the problems of forming a national innovation system based on the mechanisms of interaction within the "triple helix" and ensuring the overcoming of innovation stagnation. The authors pay special attention to the consideration of the varieties of factors of innovation inhibition, among which they highlight innovation challenges, threats and barriers, the action of which is determined by the time horizon of action. This approach allows narrowing the boundaries of the search for effective measures of state regulation in the innovation sphere. Based on the conducted research, the authors proved the need for a transition to closer international cooperation using various forms of network interaction aimed at eradicating technological inequality on a global scale.

Key Words: innovations, factors, innovative development, national economy, infrastructure, network interaction.

In accordance with international trends, the development of an innovative model on a national scale implies an expansion of the presence of innovative production in the technological structure of the economy, which is manifested, first of all, in an increase in the volume of production of innovative products. In accordance with the mechanisms of economic dynamics, innovative processes are the result of a consistent replacement of technologically related industries. The transition of the national economy to sustainable innovative growth requires maximum overcoming or elimination of the influence of destructive factors - this requires their identification by scale, strength and duration of impact. At the same time, the intention to determine universal factors without taking into account at least the stage of innovative development at which the national economy is located can lead to erroneous conclusions. It should also be taken into account that the same factor can have both a stimulating and a disincentive effect. An example is the innovative infrastructure created at the expense of budgetary funds in special economic zones, which, in the event of an underdeveloped national innovation system or the absence of appropriate demand, may be unclaimed. At the same time, in modern conditions, the stimulating role of the state remains relevant regardless of the level of innovative development of the country. World practice shows that at the initial stages of the formation of the innovation process, government regulation plays a decisive role, which is why there is a need to study the stimulating and disincentive factors of innovative development. The influence of socio-economic factors on innovation processes depends on the time horizon of action, depending on which innovative challenges, innovative threats and innovative barriers arise. The multidimensionality and combinatorial nature of innovation activities predetermine the possibility of regression, and its overcoming requires the implementation of effective organizational and managerial

decisions aimed at coordinating the actions of all participants in the innovation process. This creates conditions under which self-organization mechanisms arise, causing progressive evolutionary changes.

Methods and materials

The aim of the study is to generalize the trends and identify patterns in the mutual dependence of destructive and positive factors influencing the development of innovation processes at the macroeconomic level. The substantiation of the author's concept is based on the classical theory of stages of economic growth by W. Rostow and the paradigmatic theory of global evolutionism by E. Jantsch . This study focuses on the complex structure innovative activity from the standpoint of its distinctive features compared to traditional production, using the factual method - the study of facts recorded in modern scientific works, expert assessments and analytical developments. The evidence base was the results published in the international innovation ratings The Global Innovation Index , Digital Economy and Society Index , statistical studies of innovation indicators of the Higher School of Economics, materials of the international network of companies PricewaterhouseCoopers, international innovation networks The European Association of Development Agencies (EURADA), World Alliance for Innovation (WAINOVA), Enterprise Europe Network (EEN). The presented study is based on a combination of general scientific interdisciplinary and specialized economic methods, including analysis, synthesis, scientific analogy, inductive and deductive methods, structural analysis, which is a methodological type of system analysis, structural and logical modeling. Considerable attention is paid to the analysis of economic categories inherent in an innovation- oriented economy. The conceptual apparatus that reveals the content of the concepts of "innovative development", "innovative factors", "innovative process" has been clarified, and debatable issues have been additionally substantiated. Conceptual aspects of the stages of innovative development The expansion of innovative presence in the economy depends decisively on the ability of the economy to progressive transformation, implemented in world practice within the framework of the national innovation system and subject to sufficient potential at the national level. This predetermines the dependence of the emergence of factors that in one way or another affect innovative growth on the successes achieved by states in innovative development. The classification of innovation factors into certain types is a debatable issue and in this case it is difficult to avoid subjectivity in views and ideas. It can be assumed that there is a similarity of problems of innovation development in developing countries. Taking into account the Russian experience, we will define the most common of them. The effect of these types of factors varies significantly, their characteristics and some examples relevant to the Russian economy are given in. As for other factors that hinder innovation growth, experts mainly highlight those that relate to innovation threats and innovation barriers. These are the results reached by a group of scientists from the Higher School of Economics, which carries out statistical studies of innovation indicators on an ongoing basis. As can be seen from the figure, the most significant disincentive factors were the lack of own funds (20.5%) and the high cost of innovations (15.3%). Low demand for innovative goods and services was rated as the least significant (5.2%). A different situation and different trends regarding innovations are taking place in developed countries. Let us consider the following main areas of factor influence: agglomeration effects, infrastructure factors and the activity of international innovation networks. Agglomeration territories are a concentration of high scientific and technological potential, and therefore create an additional

effect due to the growth and spread of economic and innovative activity beyond their borders. The role of agglomerations in the global economy is increasing due to the emergence of so-called technationalism, the essence of which is focus.

The level of innovative development of the world's largest agglomerations is assessed by the international network of companies PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC), which, together with the British charitable foundation Calvert 22 Foundation, has been publishing the Creative Capital Index since 2016. The PwC methodology provides for the assessment of agglomerations based on the level of technology penetration, labor productivity, level of education, and level of development of the creative sector [3]. The index assesses the creative capital indicators of 20 Russian cities, among which, taking into account the innovative ratings, the most significant are Moscow, St. Petersburg, Kazan, Kaliningrad, Krasnodar, Krasnoyarsk, Nizhny Novgorod, and Novosibirsk. The world capitals studied include Berlin, Hong Kong, New York, London, Seoul, Sydney, and Helsinki.

In the modern world, the dominant principle of organizing innovation processes is the construction of network development models, which are open systems, the development of which is based on self-organization. This process has found expression in the creation of international innovation networks and associations, the development of which has followed the path of stimulating transnational technology transfer and promoting innovative services. In countries such as the United States, Australia, and Great Britain, innovation policy has shifted funding and incentives in the field of R & D in the direction of encouraging multi-sector innovation networks (Corley, Boardman, Bozeman, 2006). In many cases, the activity of innovation networks is expressed in the exchange of ideas, knowledge, experience, promotion of development, creation of necessary conditions, establishment of partnerships, etc., which only indirectly affects the development of innovations. Examples such networks: The European Association of Development Agencies (EURADA); World Alliance for Innovation (WAINOVA); Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) and etc. However, the results of the study of the spatio-temporal influence of embeddedness in R&D networks on the production of regional knowledge of 229 European regions included in the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS), conducted for 1998-2010, revealed positive effects arising from network integration (Wanzenböck, Piribauer, 2016). The disadvantage is the informal connections between participants in innovation networks built on declarations of cooperation, memorandums of understanding, etc., which are unstable. Conclusion This study distinguishes between approaches to understanding the essence of innovative development for developing economies and for technologically developed countries. In the first case, innovative development should be manifested not only in the expansion of the scale of innovative production, but also in the creation of conditions for the transition to a higher stage of innovative development, due to the improvement of the organizational and managerial environment and technological conditions. In the second case, one should focus on the priority of radical innovations associated with a technological revolution and the implementation of new forms of interaction between participants in the national innovation system, including at the interstate level. In the innovation process, one can talk about the opposing action of two groups of forces. One of them sets in motion the process of introducing progressive technologies into production with the subsequent diffusion of innovations, which "steps over" the borders of states, industries and markets. Another group of forces hinders innovative development or creates a situation of innovative stagnation. The situation in which

developed countries continue to develop along the path of evolutionary and revolutionary technological changes, while in developing countries the technological gap is growing, leads to a general innovation slowdown in the global space. A certain breakthrough in the unevenness of technological development is created by numerous international innovation networks. However, the nomenclature of territorial units for statistics (NUTS) remains tied to the established administrative-territorial division of the EU countries, which hinders integration. The World Alliance of International Financial Centers (World Alliance of International Financial Centers , WAIFC) , which promotes international cooperation, sustainable investment and preventing the impact of protectionism during a global health and economic emergency. As countries move to a higher level of innovative development, the role of the state changes - self-organization gradually displaces directive management and government regulation. At the same time, solving the problems of innovative development is associated not only with the effectiveness of public policy, but also with the activities of international innovation networks, which are focused to a greater extent on the development of mechanisms for financing and supporting innovative entrepreneurship within the framework of public-private partnerships.

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